

Intermediate Activity Report

Deliverable n. 2: Report on availability and status of the testbed; publication of pipeline and preliminary analysis results

CERN – Be-ys

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Project Activity Status

The QUANTUMACY project started on February 1st, 2021. The project ambition is to support the move towards confidential computing and informational self-determination by integrating the relevant technologies into core QKD-enabled services requiring key issuance and distribution, and thus lead a new approach to making data available and processed under the so-called principle of polymorphic privacy.

To do so, QUANTUMACY is deploying a small-scale, proof-of-concept platform, where existing encryption techniques are combined and extended to use the openQKD infrastructure across the different layers of the platform and test on concrete healthcare use-cases can be performed.

The initial status of the services and the deployed resources has been described in the first deliverable on April 30th, 2021 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5574517>). During the first 8 months of activities the following tasks have been performed:

- 1) **Platform deployment:** all necessary resources have been deployed at CERN. The platform is based on four dedicated nodes providing collectively the submission, storage and computing services.
- 2) **Platform Architecture:** the architecture includes the implementation of two operating modes, aggregated and federated (see Fig. 1)

Figure 1: The QUANTUMACY platform architecture

- 3) **QKD Links:** All communication between each pair of nodes is based on a simulated BB84 protocol implementation (green and red arrows in Fig. 1). The simulation software allows to generate pairs of symmetric keys that the different services can use to secure the channel, encrypt the content or both. The software also allows performing simple simulations of noise and attacks (see Fig. 2)

Figure 2: The QKDSim toolkit

- 4) **Computing Frameworks:** the platform allows to deploy simple Machine Learning/Deep Learning pipelines where the data is homomorphically encrypted by the user before submission to one or more storage nodes, then processed and the results sent back to the user. The open-source OpenFL federated learning framework has been used. The framework is being modified to replace the existing gRPC/TLS calls with QKD calls using the simulator APIs
- 5) **Use cases:** three use cases are being implemented, namely Health Risk Assessment, Chest MRI Images Classification, and Parkinson's symptoms classification, the first two using aggregated (anonymised) data and the third one using the federated learning approach with the data stored on two separate nodes (see Fig. 3).

Reference use cases

Health risk assessment (aggregated data)
(Hanyul Ryu, Gabriele Morello)

Chest MRI classification (aggregated data from Stanford AIMI)
(Jose Cabrero Holgueras, Gabriele Morello)

Parkinson's symptoms classification
(Anna Ferrari, not yet deployed)

Figure 3: The reference use cases

The project has been presented at the 2021 Conference on Quantum Security Technology Global Cooperation and Industry Revitalization Strategy (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5574538>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WMtK7geHmY>)

Planned Activities

The different components of the system have been implemented as planned and tested individually. They are now being integrated as an end-to-end demo platform, which will allow external users to test and visualise the different use cases from a public web application by December 2021.

The organisation of the test of a real QKD link between the CERN data Centre and the SIG data centre in Geneva has started and link is planned to be established by the end of October 2021 with the assistance of IDQ. Tests with a hybrid set up of simulated and real links will be performed until December 2021 (an extension to January might be possible depending on the availability of the hardware).

At the same time, discussions have started with SNUBH and KISTI in South Korea to establish a second site for cross-testing using the simulated QKD software.

The detailed definition of the block-chained based use cases has just started. It is planned to deploy the use case by the end of 2021.

As soon as the integration tests are completed, all software developed during the projects will be released under an MIT license through the github platform (where it is currently stored, albeit in a project-private repository).

The experience gathered during the execution of the project will be summarised in the form a journal article in preparation that will be submitted to a relevant journal (to be selected) in January 2022.